

Differences in the detection of virulence genes among clinical isolates of Coagulase-Negative Staphylococci

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Summary

Although Coagulase Negative Staphylococci (CoNS) have been considered for years as colonizers of the human body, it is now clear that they can cause serious infections, especially among immunocompromised patients. Various genes express for pathogenic mechanisms, including the *icaA* and *icaD* which enhance biofilm production, as well as genes than encode for staphylococcal enterotoxins (*sea*, *seb*) and the toxic shock syndrome toxin (*tst*). The aim of

this study was to detect and determine through PCR the presence and distribution of these genes in CoNS strains isolated from clinical specimens. The results of the study showed that *icaA* and *icaD* genes were present in 49% and 52% of CoNS strains respectively, while 36,5% of the strains harbored the *tst* gene. No CoNS strains harbored the enterotoxin A and B genes. The *S. epidermidis* strains harbored the *icaA/D* and *tst* genes more frequently than the remaining CoNS species (statistically significant difference, $p < 0.001$ and $p = 0.001$, respectively).

Key words

Coagulase Negative Staphylococci (CoNS); virulence genes; enterotoxins; the toxic shock syndrome toxin

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Introduction

Coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) constitute a large part of the human skin and mucosa microbiome with more than 50 species comprising the group so far.¹ Various species of CoNS are also common colonizers of the anterior nares, external ear canal and upper respiratory and gastrointestinal tract.² Given the fact also that compared to *Staphylococcus aureus*, CoNS are considered to be less virulent, in the past, most of the times, their presence in clinical samples was dismissed as contamination.³ However, recent demographic changes and continuous medical advances have led to higher life expectation which is nevertheless coupled with various comorbidities, increased numbers of immunocompromised patients and an ever-increasing use of catheters and foreign devices. As a result, CoNS have emerged as opportunistic pathogens.⁴ The most frequently isolated CoNS species in clinical samples is *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (>50% of CoNS isolates) followed by *Staphylococcus haemolyticus* and *Staphylococcus hominis*.²

The main risk factor for an infection caused by

CoNS is the existence of a foreign medical device in the human body. Therefore, foreign-body related infections (FBRIs), either local or bloodstream related, are the most common clinical entities associated with CoNS,⁵ such as catheter-related bacteremias,^{6,7} and prosthetic joint infections.⁸ In addition, in late onset neonatal sepsis (i.e., between 3 and 30 days of life), CoNS are common pathogens, especially for infants born at a lower gestational age.⁹

The most important virulence factor of CoNS is their ability to produce biofilm.¹⁰ This extracellular matrix which encapsulates bacterial aggregates allows them to evade the host's immune system and protects them against antibiotics.⁴ The accumulation of biofilm in CoNS is mainly mediated through Polysaccharide Intercellular Adhesin (PIA) whose synthesis relies on enzymes encoded in *icaA/D/B/C* genes. Co-expression of *icaA* and *icaD* genes has been found to significantly increase the amount of biofilm produced.¹¹

Another major category of Staphylococcal virulence factors are toxins, like the enterotoxins (e.g., SEA, SEB, SEC etc., encoded by the *sea/seb/sec* genes) and the Toxic shock syndrome toxin (TSST, encoded by the *tst* gene). Although they have been mostly studied in

S. aureus, the occasional ability of CoNS isolates to produce these toxins has been proved in recent years.^{12,13}

The objective of the present study was to detect the presence and distribution of genes associated with Staphylococcal virulence, more specifically *icaA*, *icaD*, *sea*, *seb*, and *tst*, among CoNS strains isolated from clinical samples of hospitalized patients.

Materials & Methods

All CoNS strains isolated from blood cultures and cultures of i.v. catheters and/or implanted cardiac devices of hospitalized patients at the Onassis Cardiac Surgery Center in Athens, Greece during a three-month period in 2022 were collected.

Genus and species identification was performed using MALDI-TOF technology (MALDI Biotyper, Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany). The minimum acceptable identification score value was set at 1.7. After identification was complete, and if multiple isolates were collected from a single patient, the first isolate per species, per clinical source, per patient was included in the study.

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed using the MIC Panel Type 33 for Gram-positive pathogens (Microscan, Dade Behring). The antibiotics tested and the respective MIC range (mg/L) were: penicillin (0.12-8), ceftaxime (4), oxacillin (0.25-2), ceftaroline (0.5-1), nitrofurantoin (32-64), gentami-

cin (1-8), tobramycin (1-8), amikacin (8-32), mupirocin (256), chloramphenicol (8-16), erythromycin (0.5-4), clindamycin (0.25-2), daptomycin (1-4), ciprofloxacin (1-2), levofloxacin (1-4), moxifloxacin (0.5-1), norfloxacin (4-8), fosfomycin (32-64), linezolid (1-4), pristinamycin (1-2), fusidic acid (2), minocycline (1-8), tetracycline (1-8), vancomycin (0.25-16), teicoplanin (1-16), quinupristin-dalfopristin (1-4), co-trimoxazole (2/38-4/76) and rifampicin (0.5-2).

DNA extraction was performed from colonies harvested from a 24h culture on 5% sheep blood agar plates (Bioprep, Gerakas, Greece) using the Qiagen QIAamp DNA mini kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), according to the manufacturer's instructions.

PCR reactions were performed as single reactions for the *icaA* and *icaD* genes and as multiplex reactions for the *sea*, *seb* and *tst* genes, according to previously published protocols.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ The primers used are depicted in Table 1. Each single PCR was carried out in a total volume of 20 µl containing 10µl of GoTaq® 2X Colorless Master Mix (Promega Corporation, USA), and 0.1 µM of forward and reverse primers. Amplification was performed in a Bio-Rad iCycler Thermal Cycler using an initial cycle at 95°C for 5 min, followed by 35 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 30 sec, annealing of the primers at 55°C for 30 sec and extension at 72°C for 30 sec, and a final step at 72°C for 5 min. The multiplex PCR was carried out in a total volume of 25µl containing 12 µl of GoTaq® 2X Colorless Master Mix, 0.1 µM of forward and reverse primer for *sea* and *tst* genes, 0.2 µM of forward and reverse primer for

Table 1 The sequences of the primers used for PCR.

Gene	Primer sequence	Product size (bp)	Reference
<i>icaA</i>	F: 5'-TCTCTTGCAGGAGCAATCAA-3'	188	15
	R: 5'-TCAGGCACTAACATCCAGCA-3'		
<i>icaD</i>	F: 5'-ATGGTCAAGCCCAGACAGAG-3'	198	15
	R: 5'-CGTGTTTTCAACATTTAATGCAA-3'		
<i>tst</i>	F: 5'-ATCGTAAGCCCTTTGTTG -3'	578	16
	R: 5'-GTGGATCCGTCATTCATTG-3'		
<i>sea</i>	F: 5'-CATTGCCCTAACGTTGAC -3'	619	16
	R: 5'-CGAAGGTTCTGTAGAAGTATGG -3'		
<i>seb</i>	F: 5'-CTAAACCAGATGAGTTGCAC-3'	489	16
	R: 5'-CCAAATAGTGACGAGTTAGG-3'		

seb. Amplification was performed in a Bio-Rad iCycler Thermal Cycler using an initial cycle at 95°C for 15min, followed by 35 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 2 min, annealing of the primers at 51°C for 1 min, and extension at 72°C for 1 min, and a final step at 72°C for 5 min.

All PCR products were visualized on a 2% agarose gel under UV illumination and compared to a standard 100bp Ladder (Nippon Genetics, Europe).

Statistical evaluation was performed using χ^2 and significant difference was set at $p < 0.01$.

Results and discussion

A total of 90 CoNS strains were included in the study and were identified as follows: 63 *S. epidermidis*, nine *S. haemolyticus*, eight *S. hominis*, four *S. capitis*, three *S. warneri*, two *S. pettenkoferi* and one *S. pasteuri*. The mean MALDI identification score value was higher than 2 for every isolate.

A total of 69 isolates (evenly distributed among the species) were resistant to antistaphylococcal penicillins (MRCoNS), of which a number of strains were additionally resistant to one or more of the four major antibiotics for MRCoNS (vancomycin, teicoplanin, linezolid and daptomycin) as follows: resistance to teicoplanin was exhibited in 18 isolates (20%) comprising 14 *S. epidermidis* and four *S. haemolyticus*, whilst eight *S. epidermidis* strains (8,8%) were resistant to linezolid, four *S. epidermidis* (4,4%) were resistant to vancomycin and three *S. epidermidis* isolates (3,3%) were resistant to daptomycin. All MSCoNS were susceptible to these four antibiotics. Resistance patterns among *S. epidermidis* and all other CoNS species are shown in Table 2.

Our study showed that although methicillin resistance was detected and evenly distributed among all

CoNS species, resistance to the four above mentioned antibiotics was more frequently detected among MR *S. epidermidis* than other species of MRCoNS, although this difference was not statistically significant.

The reported percentage of methicillin resistance in 76% of the isolated CoNS strains confirms previously published studies such as the one by Asante et al.¹⁷ in which 76.4% of the CoNS strains isolated from blood stream infections were methicillin resistant, or the one by Al-Tamimi et al.¹⁸ in which among CoNS strains isolated from the nostrils of hospitalized patients 73% were methicillin resistant. Methicillin resistance is usually accomplished by the expression of *mecA* gene which encodes for PBP2a with low affinity to penicillin and other beta-lactams.¹⁹ As far as teicoplanin is concerned, the reported resistance of CoNS strains varies from 10.6% to 33% in different studies with our results (20%) falling in between.^{20,21} However, the reported percentages of resistance to the remaining antibiotics (i.e. 4.4% for vancomycin, 3.3% for daptomycin and 8.8% for linezolid) are clearly higher than previously published data which show less than 0,3% resistance to vancomycin and daptomycin^{19,20} and 0.3-1.3% resistance to linezolid.^{19,22} In addition, there are scarce reports of CoNS strains with combined resistance to those antibiotics as well. The main mechanisms through which CoNS develop resistance to antibiotics require mutations to genes encoding the target proteins of each antibiotic category. For example, mutations to genes such as *mprF* and *rpoB* which result in changes in bacterial cell wall thickness, and membrane fluidity and charge can lead to resistance to daptomycin. Furthermore, mutations which modify 23S rRNA of the 50S ribosomal subunit prevent the binding of linezolid rendering the strain resistant.¹⁹ Finally, acquisition of plasmid DNA which bears resistance genes from other species such as *VanA* operon can lead to altered peptidoglycan which cannot bind

Table 2 Antibiotic resistance patterns.

Resistance	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	Other CoNS
Tei	6	4
Lzd	1	0
Van + Tei	1	0
Tei + Lzd	4	0
Van + Tei + Lzd + Dap	3	0
None	48	23

Tei: teicoplanin, Lzd: linezolid, Van: vancomycin, Dap: daptomycin

vancomycin.²³

The genes *icaA*, *icaD* and *tst* were detected in 49.0%, 52.0% and 36.5% of the isolates respectively, whilst the *sea* and *seb* genes were not detected in any CoNS isolate. Interestingly, both the *icaA/D* genes and the *tst* gene were found statistically significantly more often among *S. epidermidis* strains than in other CoNS species ($p < 0.001$ for *icaA/D* genes, $p = 0.001$ for *tst* gene), as shown in Table 3. No correlation between antibiotic resistance and the aforementioned genes was found.

The reported percentages for the *icaA*, *icaD* and *tst* genes (regardless of species) are in accordance with previous studies which observed rates of 57-58% for the *icaA* gene, 56-60% for the *icaD* and 31.4% for the *tst* gene in CoNS isolates.²⁴⁻²⁶ More specifically, in the study by Ahmed et al. 58% of CoNS isolated from

nasal colonization of neonates in the ICU were positive for the *icaA* gene and 60% for the *icaD* gene.²⁴ Accordingly, in a study by Hosbul et al. in CoNS isolated from blood cultures, *icaA* and *icaD* were detected in 5.1% and 56.1% of the strains respectively.²⁵ As far as the toxin producing genes are concerned, Wierzychowska et al. found that 31.4% of CoNS isolated from ready-to-eat food were positive for the *tst* gene whilst no isolate bearing the *sea* or *seb* genes was detected.²⁶

Nevertheless, a statistically significant difference in the frequency of those genes between CoNS species, such as the one reported here, has not been described before and in that respect more studies are needed in order to ascertain whether this observation is the result of the prevailing local flora of the hospital, or it can be further extrapolated to characterize the CoNS species.

Table 3 Number of isolates bearing each gene in *S. epidermidis* or other CoNS species.

Species	No of isolates	<i>icaA</i> (+)	<i>icaA</i> (-)	<i>icaD</i> (+)	<i>icaD</i> (-)	<i>tst</i> (+)	<i>tst</i> (-)	<i>sea</i> (+)	<i>sea</i> (-)	<i>seb</i> (+)	<i>seb</i> (-)
<i>S. epidermidis</i>	63	43	20	44	19	30	33	0	63	0	63
Other CoNS species	27	1	26	3	24	3	24	0	27	0	27

Περίληψη

Διαφορές στην ανίχνευση μολυσματικών γονιδίων μεταξύ κλινικών στελεχών κοαγκουλάση αρνητικών Σταφυλόκοκκων

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Αν και οι κοαγκουλάση-αρνητικοί σταφυλόκοκκοι (Coagulase Negative Staphylococci, CoNS) θεωρούνται εδώ και χρόνια ως αποικιστές του ανθρώπινου σώματος, είναι πλέον σαφές ότι μπορούν να προκαλέσουν σοβαρές λοιμώξεις, ειδικά σε ανοσοκατεσταλμένους ασθενείς. Διάφορα γονίδια σχετίζονται με παθογόνους μηχανισμούς, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των *icaA* και *icaD*, που ενισχύουν την παραγωγή βιομεμβράνης, καθώς και γονίδια που κωδικοποιούν για τις σταφυλοκοκκικές εντεροτοξίνες (*sea*, *seb*) και την τοξίνη του συνδρόμου του τοξικού σοκ (*tst*). Ο στόχος αυτής της μελέτης ήταν να ανιχνεύσει και να προσδιορίσει μέσω PCR την παρουσία και κατανομή αυτών των γονιδίων σε στελέχη CoNS που απομονώθηκαν από κλινικά δείγματα. Τα αποτελέσματα της μελέτης έδειξαν ότι τα γονίδια *icaA* και *icaD* υπήρχαν στο 49% και 52% των στελεχών CoNS αντίστοιχα, ενώ το 36,5% των στελεχών έφεραν το γονίδιο *tst*. Κανένα στέλεχος CoNS δεν έφερε τα γονίδια της εντεροτοξίνης A και B. Τα στελέχη *S. epidermidis* έφεραν τα γονίδια *icaA/D* και *tst* πιο συχνά από τα υπόλοιπα είδη CoNS (στατιστικά σημαντική διαφορά, $p < 0,001$ και $p = 0,001$, αντίστοιχα).

Λέξεις κλειδιά

κοαγκουλάση-αρνητικοί σταφυλόκοκκοι κοαγκουλάσης (CoNS), γονίδια λοιμογόνου δράσης, εντεροτοξίνες, τοξίνη του συνδρόμου τοξικού σοκ

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